

Questionnaire: Shared Decision-Making and Decision Aids in Breast Cancer Care

Please select your current position/role in breast health practice:

- Medical oncologist
- Radiation oncologist
- Radiologist
- Breast health is not my clinical area
- Other (please specify)

Section 1: Shared decision-making (SDM)

There are no right or wrong answers to the following question. To answer it, please look at the examples given below. Each example shows a different approach to how a decision about treatment can be made with a patient having a clear diagnosis. Now think about your approach to decision making with breast cancer patients. On a scale of 1-5, please indicate your level of comfort in using each of the 4 approaches to treatment decision making:

	Not comfortable				Extremely comfortable
1 After reviewing the medical records and examining the patient, I decide on a suitable treatment and share it with the patient. I give information about the treatment, including risks and benefits. The patient accepts the treatment I recommend.	1	2	3	4	5
2 After reviewing the medical records and examining the patient, I present the available treatment options. Information about risks and benefits of each option is discussed. I invite the patient to ask any question. Then I recommend a treatment that my patient accepts.	1	2	3	4	5
3 After reviewing the medical records and examining the patient, I present the available treatment options. Information about risks and benefits of each option is discussed. I ask the patient to decide on a treatment because she/he is the best to make such decision. She/he decides and informs me about her/his preference.	1	2	3	4	5
4 After reviewing the medical records and examining the patient, I present the available treatment options. Information about risks and benefits of each option is discussed. I invite the patient to ask any question. Then I ask her/his preference for a treatment given her/his lifestyle and the issues that are important to her/him. Together we decide on a treatment to implement.	1	2	3	4	5

From your perspective, how important is each of the following to a process of treatment decision-making?

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
1 Clinician giving information to the patient	1	2	3	4	5
2 Patient giving information about what is important to her/him	1	2	3	4	5
3 Clinician giving a treatment recommendation	1	2	3	4	5
4 Patient deciding on their treatment without the clinician	1	2	3	4	5
5 Discussing pros and cons of treatment options with the patient	1	2	3	4	5

6	Clinician and patient together agreeing on a treatment option	1	2	3	4	5
7	Engaging with patients' family members or caregiver, if relevant	1	2	3	4	5

Shared decision-making is regarded as contributing to more patient-centred healthcare. Shared decision-making is defined in this study as a process of collaboration between patients and clinicians to reach a joint decision about care involving multiple clinically appropriate options.

Please tell us how much do you agree or disagree with the following statements:

		Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
1	Patients can interpret shared decision-making as a sign of incompetence	1	2	3	4
2	Patients with lower levels of education are more challenging to engage in shared decision-making	1	2	3	4
3	Patients need decision aids (leaflets, videos, apps) to engage in their health decisions	1	2	3	4
4	Organizational support (top management, peers) is necessary to implement shared decision-making	1	2	3	4
5	Shared decision-making requires appropriate training of health professionals	1	2	3	4
6	Patient associations can aid shared decision-making by disseminating material and giving support to patients	1	2	3	4
7	Putting shared decision-making into practice will lead to improved patient satisfaction, mental health and quality of life	1	2	3	4
8	Lack of time and resources (staff, equipment, space) makes it difficult to engage in shared decision-making	1	2	3	4

Section 2: Patient decision aids (DAs)

The UK National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) identifies patient decision aids as enablers for shared decision-making. A patient decision aid is defined here as a tool or technology in various formats (paper-based, online, video, audio, etc.) designed to provide information and facilitate patients in deciding a treatment with their clinician.

Is any patient decision aid available in your practice to support treatment decisions?

Yes

No

I don't know

If yes:

Do you use any patient decision aid to facilitate treatment decisions?

Yes

No

Which of the following patient decision aids do you use to facilitate treatment decisions? Tick all that apply.

Question prompt list or conversation aid

Option Grid and Picture Option Grid (one-page leaflets with a summary table to enable rapid comparison between options.

Picture option grid is a pictorial version of the option grid)

Video material

Interactive, web-based tools (e.g., online learning modules, mobile apps, informative websites, risk calculators)

Paper-based tools (e.g. booklet, brochure, workbook, letters from cancer survivors)

Coaching sessions (e.g. trained nurses, cancer survivors, patient advocates)

Other (please specify)

[For those previously selected] Out of a population of 10 patients, with how many patients do you use them?

	1-2 patients	3-5 patients	6-8 patients	9-10 patients
1 Question prompt list or conversation aid				
2 Option Grid and Picture Option Grid				
3 Video material				
4 Interactive, web-based tools				
5 Paper-based tools				
6 Coaching sessions				
7 Other				

[For those previously selected] When do you use them?

	Before the consultation	During the consultation	After the consultation
1 Question prompt list or conversation aid			
2 Option Grid and Picture Option Grid			
3 Video material			
4 Interactive, web-based tools			
5 Paper-based tools			
6 Coaching sessions			
7 Other			

If no:

If a patient decision aid were available in your organization/country, would you use it in deciding a treatment with your patients?

Yes

No

What aspects do you think might be relevant for a patient decision aid if you were to use it?

Evidence-based information it contains

Time spent using it

Being accessible in multiple formats, printed or online, and in different languages

Integration into the workflow and various electronic health record systems

Which of the following best describes the reason(s) for not using a patient decision aid?

Lack of an organized system to distribute decision aids

Patients' characteristics (eg. literacy, age)

Insufficient time to spend with patient(s)

Insufficient training about decision aids

I use other strategies to facilitate patient's decision

Section 3: Demographics

Please select the country in which you currently practice: _____

Your Breast Cancer Unit is:

Certified at national level

Certified at European level

Not certified

I don't know

How many Breast Cancer patients does your unit treat annually?

<100

101-300
301-500
>501

What is your seniority? Seniority is defined as the number of years since the end of your residency. _____

Please indicate your gender:

Male

Female

Non-binary / Third gender

Prefer not to say